

HeMoVal Study – Statistical Analysis Plan

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1 Abbreviations and Definitions

aSAH	aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhage
AUC	area under the curve
aVSP	angiographic vasospasm
CRF	case report form
eCRF	electronic case report form
CSF	cerebrospinal fluid
DCI	delayed cerebral ischemia
DIND	delayed ischemic neurological deficit
EVD	external ventricular drainage
GCP	good clinical practice
GCS	glasgow coma scale
GOSE	glasgow outcome scale extended
Hb	hemoglobin
LD	lumbar drainage
mRS	modified rankin scale
ROC	receiver operating characteristic
SAH-SBI	subarachnoid hemorrhage related secondary brain injury
SAP	statistical analysis plan
SE	serious event
SOP	standard operating procedure
TMF	trial master file

2 Introduction

2.1 Background and rationale

Up to two-thirds of patients after aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhage (aSAH) develop secondary brain injury (SAH-SBI), typically between day 4 and 14 after aneurysm rupture,¹ which significantly influences clinical outcome. SAH-SBI may manifest as angiographic vasospasms of large cerebral arteries (aVSP),² delayed cerebral ischemia (DCI) with radiologic demarcation of ischemic brain areas or clinically evident delayed ischemic neurologic deficits (DIND).³ There is an unmet need for identifying patients at high risk for SAH-SBI. Although widely used – owing the lack of superior alternatives – clinical scores,^{4,5} radiological scores,^{6–8} and day-to-day assessment with transcranial doppler sonography^{9,10} show a limited accuracy¹¹ and there is no clinically established biomarker to reliably monitor for SAH-SBI. Several research groups, including ours, have experimentally defined that cell-free hemoglobin (Hb) induces pathophysiological processes reflecting specific features of SAH-SBI, such as vasospasm, lipid oxidation, and neuronal damage.^{12,13} In a recently finalized clinical pilot study,¹⁴ we found that the high-risk phase for SAH-SBI, between days 4 and 14 after aSAH, coincides with increased levels of cerebrospinal fluid Hb (CSF-Hb). We found very strong evidence for a positive association between the concentration of daily measured external ventricular drain (EVD) based CSF-Hb and the occurrence of SAH-SBI, defined as the composite outcome of aVSP, DCI or DIND. We identified CSF-Hb as a potential biomarker for SAH-SBI considerably exceeding the discrimination ability of established methods. However, our clinical pilot study was limited by its single-center design and the restricted number of patients. This multicenter study aims to validate and generalize our findings regarding the positive association between CSF-Hb and SAH-SBI, and the discrimination ability of CSF-Hb for SAH-SBI.

2.2 Research hypothesis

The null hypothesis is that there is no association between the concentration of EVD based CSF-Hb and the occurrence of SAH-SBI during the first 14 days post-SAH. The alternative hypothesis is that there is an association between the two.

3 Study Objectives and Endpoints

3.1 Study Objectives

(ICH E3; 8.)

3.1.1 Primary objective

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the strength of association between EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) and SAH-SBI (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort.

3.1.2 Secondary objectives

The secondary objectives are to investigate:

- a. Temporal profiles and dependence of EVD and lumbar drain (LD) based CSF-Hb:
 - i. The temporal profile (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of EVD based CSF-Hb in the EVD cohort.
 - ii. The temporal profile (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of LD based CSF-Hb in the LD cohort.

- iii. Difference (per day and overall) between EVD and LD based CSF-Hb from day 1 to day 14 post-SAH.
 - iv. The strength of association between EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning of day 1 to 14 post-SAH) and aneurysm location (assessed at study inclusion), hematoma volume (assessed at study inclusion), presence of intraventricular hemorrhage (assessed at study inclusion) and day post-SAH in the EVD cohort.
 - v. The strength of association between LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning of day 1 to 14 post-SAH) and aneurysm location (assessed at study inclusion), hematoma volume (assessed at study inclusion), presence of intraventricular hemorrhage (assessed at study inclusion) and day post-SAH in the LD cohort.
- b. EVD based CSF-Hb and SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND in the EVD cohort:
- i. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND in the EVD cohort.
 - ii. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of EVD based CSF-Hb stratified by the presence or absence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, or DIND in the EVD cohort.
 - iii. The strength of association between EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) and aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort.
 - iv. The discrimination ability of EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort.
 - v. The discrimination ability of EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for the first occurrence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort.
 - vi. The discrimination ability of EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning of day X) for the first occurrence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of day X+1) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort.
 - vii. The discrimination ability of EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during day 4 and day 14 post-SAH in the EVD cohort.
- c. LD based CSF-Hb and SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND in the LD cohort:
- i. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND in the LD cohort.
 - ii. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of LD based CSF-Hb stratified by the presence or absence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, or DIND in the LD cohort.
 - iii. The strength of association between LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) and SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the LD cohort.
 - iv. The discrimination ability of LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the LD cohort.
 - v. The discrimination ability of LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for the first occurrence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the LD cohort.
 - vi. The discrimination ability of LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning of day X) for the first occurrence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of day X+1) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the LD cohort.
 - vii. The discrimination ability of LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during day 4 and day 14 post-SAH in the LD cohort.
- d. EVD based CSF-Hb and 3-months follow-up status:

- i. The strength of association between EVD based CSF-Hb during the first 14 days post-SAH and chronic hydrocephalus at 12 weeks follow-up in the EVD cohort.
 - ii. The strength of association between EVD based CSF-Hb during the first 14 days post-SAH and functional outcome (GOSE, mRS) at 12 weeks follow-up in the EVD cohort.
- e. LD based CSF-Hb and 3-months follow-up status:
 - i. The strength of association between LD based CSF-Hb during the first 14 days post-SAH and chronic hydrocephalus at 12 weeks follow-up in the LD cohort.
 - ii. The strength of association between LD based CSF-Hb during the first 14 days post-SAH and functional outcome (GOSE, mRS) at 12 weeks follow-up in the LD cohort.

3.2 Endpoints

(ICH E9; 2.2.2)

3.2.1 CSF-Hb (Biomarker)

CSF-Hb constitutes the biomarker assessed in this study. CSF sampling will be performed via EVD or LD, depending on the patient's access to the CSF space. CSF will be sampled during the first 14 days post-SAH on a daily basis in the morning, always at approximately the same time. Absorption spectra in the visual range between 350 and 650 nm will be measured and CSF-Hb levels (oxyhemoglobin) will be quantified using spectral deconvolution, as described previously.^{12,14} CSF-Hb will be handled as a continuous variable [mcmol/l].

3.2.2 Primary endpoint

The primary endpoint of this study is the occurrence of SAH-SBI. SAH-SBI is a categorical variable that will be derived as a composite from the categorical secondary endpoints aVSP, DCI, and DIND: If any one or more of the three secondary endpoints (aVSP, DCI, or DIND) is present on the corresponding day, SAH-SBI is considered to be present. If neither information on aVSP (no imaging performed), nor DCI (no imaging performed) or DIND (patient not clinically assessable) could be obtained, SAH-SBI is considered to be non-assessable. In any other instance, SAH-SBI is considered not to be present.

3.2.3 Secondary endpoints

Secondary endpoints, which will be assessed during the first 14 days post-SAH on a daily basis in the afternoon, always at approximately the same time:

- a. Angiographic vasospasms (aVSP): Categorical variable [present, absent or no imaging performed].
- b. Delayed cerebral ischemia (DCI): Categorical variable [present, absent or no imaging performed].
- c. Delayed ischemic neurologic deficits (DIND): Categorical variable [present, absent or non-assessable].
- d. Triple H therapy: Categorical variable [no or yes].
- e. Spasmolysis: Categorical variable [no or yes].
- f. Surgical decompression: Categorical variable [no or yes].

Secondary endpoints, which will be assessed at the 12 weeks (+/- 2 weeks) follow-up:

- g. Chronic hydrocephalus: Categorical variable [present, absent, shunt before aSAH].
- h. Glasgow Outcome Scale Extended (GOSE): Ordinal variable [1-8].
- i. modified Rankin Scale (mRS): Ordinal variable [0-6].

3.2.4 Demographic/baseline measures

Measures assessed at the time of study inclusion (usually within 24 hours of hospital admission):

- a. Patient demographics:
 - i. Age: Continuous variable [years].
 - ii. Sex: Categorical variable [female, male].
- b. Medical history:
 - i. Antithrombotics: Categorical variable [none, antiplatelets (AP), anticoagulants (AC), antiplatelets and anticoagulants (AP&AC)].
 - ii. Diabetes mellitus: Categorical variable [no, yes].
 - iii. Hypertension: Categorical variable [no, yes].
 - iv. Coronary artery disease: Categorical variable [no, yes].
 - v. Smoking: Categorical variable [current, quit, never].
- c. Clinical assessment:
 - i. Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS): Ordinal variable [3-15].
 - ii. Pupil status: Categorical variable [normal, anisocoria, bilateral mydriasis].
 - iii. Cranial nerve deficit: Categorical variable [no, yes].
 - iv. Focal neurological deficit: Categorical variable [no, motor, sensory, motor and sensory].
 - v. Headache: Categorical variable [no, minimal, moderate, severe].
 - vi. Neck stiffness: Categorical variable [no, slight, pronounced].
- d. Clinical SAH scores at admission:
 - i. World Federation of Neurological Surgeons (WFNS) grade: Ordinal variable [1-5].
 - ii. Hunt & Hess grade: Ordinal variable [1-5].
- e. Radiological features:
 - i. Aneurysm location: Categorical variable [Anterior cerebral artery (ACA), anterior communicating artery (ACOM), anterior choroidal artery (AntCh), anterior inferior cerebellar artery (AICA), basilar artery not involving the tip (basilar others), basilar artery tip (basilar tip), non-paraophthalmic internal carotid artery (ICA others), paraophthalmic internal carotid artery (ICA paraophthalmic), middle cerebral artery (MCA), posterior cerebral artery (PCA), posterior communicating artery (PCOM), posterior inferior cerebellar artery (PICA), superior cerebellar artery (SCA), vertebral artery (VA)].
 - ii. Aneurysm size: Continuous variable [mm].
 - iii. Intracerebral hemorrhage: Categorical variable [no, yes].
 - iv. Intraventricular hemorrhage: Categorical variable [no, yes].
- f. Radiological SAH scores at admission:
 - i. Modified Fisher grade: Ordinal variable [1-4].
 - ii. Barrow Neurological Institute (BNI) grade: Ordinal variable [1-5].
- g. Aneurysm therapy: Categorical variable [bypass, clipping, coiling, flow diverter, others, none].
Hematoma volume: Continuous variable with one decimal figure [ccm], range 0.0 - 5000.0 ccm.
Assessed on the initial CT scan in a second step. The CT scan will be uploaded by the local investigators in coded form (identifying information replaced by patient ID) to a HIN-secured platform provided by the sponsor, from where automated centralized quantification of hematoma volume is performed at the sponsor site. This is done blinded to the patients' CSF-Hb values and study outcomes.

3.2.5 Safety endpoints

Safety endpoints, which will be assessed during the first 14 days post-SAH on a daily basis in the afternoon, always at approximately the same time:

- j. CSF infection: Categorical variable [no, infection, colonization, contamination].
- k. Revision due to surgical site infection at the EVD skin entrance: Categorical variable [no, yes]

4 Study Methods

4.1 General Study Design and Plan

(ICH E3;9)

The study is configured as a prospective international multicenter observational study with blinding of clinical assessment to CSF-sampling.

4.2 General Study Population and Eligibility Criteria

(ICH E3;9.3. ICH E9;2.2.1)

General study population: The study population consists of patients admitted to a tertiary care center due to an aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhage. The primary objective of the study focuses on patients included with EVD while secondary objectives consider patients with both, EVD and LD as well as patients without any drainage system.

Eligibility criteria:

Participants fulfilling all of the following *inclusion* criteria are eligible for the study:

- Age \geq 18 years.
- Hospital admission due to an aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhage (diagnosis radiologically confirmed)

The presence of any of the following *exclusion* criteria will lead to exclusion of the participant:

- Non-aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhage (eg. trauma, perimesencephalic subarachnoid hemorrhage).
- Participation in another study with CSF sampling or an interventional medical product within the 30 days preceding and during the present study.
- Previous enrollment into the current study.

4.3 Blinding

(ICH E3; 9.4.3, 9.4.6. ICH E9; 2.3.1, 2.3.2)

The following assessments in this study include blinding:

- a. The clinical assessment of patients for the primary and secondary endpoints (done in the afternoon) is blinded to CSF sampling (performed in the morning), since the macroscopic aspect of CSF after centrifugation may provide an indication of the CSF-Hb level.
- b. CSF-Hb measurements are performed by a person blinded to the patients demographic/baseline measures and their clinical assessment/endpoints.
- c. The quantification of the hematoma volume is performed by a person blinded to the patients CSF sampling/CSF-Hb values and their clinical assessment/endpoints.

4.4 Study Assessments

(ICH E3; 9.5.1. ICH E9; 2.2.2)

The assessments in this study are divided into the following phases:

- a. *Enrollment*: At hospital admission (usually within 24 hours).
- b. *Baseline assessment*: Collection of demographic and baseline data, directly after study inclusion.
- c. *Monitoring*: Starts after baseline assessment, at the earliest on day 1 post-SAH up to a maximum of 14 days post-SAH. During this period, a daily sampling of 2 ml CSF is performed, if the patient has an EVD or LD as per routine procedure. The sampling will be done in the morning. In the afternoon, a daily clinical assessment for SAH-SBI, co-interventions and complications will be performed in all included patients.
- d. *Follow-up*: At 12 weeks postSAH, assessing the dependence on a ventriculoperitoneal shunt and the functional status of the patients.
- e. *Measurements*: CSF-Hb, hematoma volume.
- f. *Unscheduled*: Serious events.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the HeMoVal study: Graphical representation of the different phases of assessment (enrollment, baseline assessment, monitoring, 3-months follow-up), measurements, and statistical analysis in the HeMoVal study.

Table 1. Assessment table of the HeMoVal study. Overview of the different study periods with the corresponding assessments and schedule.

Study periods	Enrollment	Baseline assessment	Monitoring	12 weeks follow-up	Measurements
Visit Number	0		1 – max. 14	15	N/A
Time	Hospital admission		Daily after inclusion for max. 14 days postSAH	+12 weeks after event (+/- 2 weeks)	N/A
Eligibility Criteria	x				
Patient information & consenting	x				
Demographic/baseline measures	x				
CSF-sampling			x (daily, if EVD/LD)		
aVSP			x (daily, if imaging)		
DCI			x (daily, if imaging)		
DIND			x (daily, if assessable)		
Spasmolysis			x (daily)		
Intracerebroventricular rtPA			x (daily)		
Triple H therapy			x (daily)		
Surgical decompression			x (daily)		
Nimodipine therapy			x (daily)		
CSF infection			x (daily)		

Surgical site infection			x (daily)		
Chronic hydrocephalus				x	
GOSE				x	
mRS				x	
Hematoma volume					x
CSF-Hb					x

4.4.1 Demographic/baseline measures

Measures assessed at the time of study inclusion (usually within 24 hours of hospital admission) by a trained member of the clinical study team:

h. Patient demographics:

- i. Age: Continuous variable [years].
- ii. Sex: Categorical variable [female, male].

i. Medical history:

- i. Antithrombotics: Antithrombotics used by the patient before hospital admission? Categorical variable [none, AP, AC, AP&AC]. None = No antithrombotics used by the patient before admission. AP = Patient used antiplatelets (e.g. aspirin, clopidogrel) before hospital admission. AC = Patient used anticoagulants (e.g. marcoumar/warfarin, rivaroxaban) before hospital admission. AP&AC = Patient used both, antiplatelets and anticoagulants before hospital admission. Missing data = No information on antithrombotics before hospital admission.
- ii. Diabetes mellitus: Known diabetes mellitus before hospital admission? Categorical variable [no, yes]. Missing data = No information available on possible diabetes mellitus.
- iii. Hypertension: Known hypertension before hospital admission? Categorical variable [no, yes]. Missing data = No information available on possible hypertension.
- iv. Coronary artery disease: Known coronary artery disease before hospital admission? Categorical variable [no, yes]. Missing data = No information available on possible coronary artery disease.
- v. Smoking: Smoking status of the patient at hospital admission? Categorical variable [current, quit, never]. Current = Patient is a current smoker. Quit = Patient quit smoking. Never = Patient never smoked. Missing data = No information available on smoking status.

j. Clinical assessment:

- i. Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) at hospital admission (or before intubation, if admitted in an intubated state): Ordinal variable [3-15]. GCS = eye opening response + best verbal response + best motor response. Eye opening response: 4 = spontaneously, 3 = to speech, 2 = to pain, 1 = no response. Best verbal response: 5 = oriented to time, place

and person, 4 = confused, 3 = inappropriate words, 2 = incomprehensible sounds, 1 = no response. Best motor response: 6 = obeys commands, 5 = moves to localized pain, 4 = flexion withdrawal from pain, 3 = abnormal flexion (decorticate), 2 = abnormal extension (decerebrate), 1 = no response.

- ii. Pupil status: What is the patient's pupil status at hospital admission? Categorical variable [normal, anisocoria, bilateral mydriasis]. Normal = Isocoria / no pathological mydriasis. Anisocoria = Unilateral pathological mydriasis. Bilateral mydriasis = Bilateral pathological mydriasis. Missing data = In case the patient's eyes can not be clinically assessed.
 - iii. Cranial nerve deficit: Cranial nerve deficit at hospital admission (except abnormal pupil status)? Categorical variable [no, yes, missing data]. Missing data = In case the patient can not be clinically assessed (eg. sedation).
 - iv. Focal neurological deficit: Does the patient suffer from new focal neurological deficits of the extremities at hospital admission? Categorical variable [no, motor, sensory, motor and sensory]. Missing data = In case the patient can not be clinically assessed (eg. sedation).
 - v. Headache: Does the patient suffer from headache at hospital admission / before intubation? Categorical variable [no, minimal, moderate, severe]. Missing data = In case the patient can not be clinically assessed (eg. sedation).
 - vi. Neck stiffness: Does the patient suffer from neck stiffness at hospital admission? Categorical variable [no, slight, pronounced]. Missing data = In case the patient can not be clinically assessed (eg. sedation).
- k. Clinical SAH scores at admission:
- i. World Federation of Neurological Surgeons (WFNS) grade: What is the WFNS SAH grade of the patient at hospital admission? Ordinal variable [1-5]. 1 = GCS 15 without focal neurological deficits. 2 = GCS 13-14 without focal neurological deficits. 3 = GCS 13-14 with focal neurological deficits. 4 = GCS 7-12 (with or without focal neurological deficits). 5 = GCS < 7 (with or without focal neurological deficits).
 - ii. Hunt & Hess grade: What is the Hunt&Hess SAH grade of the patient at hospital admission? Ordinal variable [1-5]. 1 = Asymptomatic or minimal headache and slight neck stiffness. 2 = Moderate to severe headache; neck stiffness; no neurologic deficit except cranial nerve palsy. 3 = Drowsy; minimal neurologic deficit. 4 = Stuporous; moderate to severe hemiparesis; possible early decerebrate rigidity and vegetative disturbances. 5 = Deep coma; decerebrate rigidity; moribund.
- l. Radiological features:
- i. Aneurysm location: Anatomical location of the aneurysm? Categorical variable [ACA, ACOM, AntCh, AICA, basilar others, basilar tip, ICA others, ICA paraophthalmic, MCA, PCA, PCOM, PICA, SCA, VA]. ACA = Anterior cerebral artery distal to the anterior communicating artery (e.g. pericallosal artery, callosomarginal artery). ACOM = Anterior communicating artery. AntCh = Anterior choroidal artery. AICA = Anterior inferior cerebellar artery. Basilar_others = Basilar artery aneurysm not involving the tip (typically from pontine branches). Basilar_tip = Basilar artery tip aneurysm. ICA_others = Non-paraophthalmic ICA (e.g. cavernous blisters). ICA_paraophthalmic = Ophthalmic or superior hypophyseal artery. MCA = Middle cerebral artery. PCA = Posterior cerebral artery. PCOM = Posterior communicating artery. PICA = Posterior inferior cerebellar artery. SCA: Superior cerebellar artery. VA = Vertebral artery.
 - ii. Aneurysm size: Max. diameter of the aneurysm in mm. Measured on the initial CTA or DSA. Continuous variable in [mm] with one decimal figure.

- iii. Intracerebral hemorrhage: Presence of intracerebral/parenchymal hemorrhage on the initial CT scan? Categorical variable [no, yes].
- iv. Intraventricular hemorrhage: Presence of intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) on the initial CT scan. (A hematoma bursting into the ventricular system is considered an IVH. A pure retrograde redistribution of blood into the ventricular system, however, is not considered an IVH.) Categorical variable [no, yes].
- m. Radiological SAH scores at admission:
 - i. Modified Fisher grade: What is the modified Fisher grade of the patient at hospital admission? Ordinal variable [1-4]. 1 = Focal or diffuse thin SAH, no IVH. 2 = Focal or diffuse thin SAH, with IVH. 3 = Thick SAH, no IVH. 4 = Thick SAH, with IVH.
 - ii. Barrow Neurological Institute (BNI) grade: What is the Barrow Neurological Institute (BNI) grade of the patient at hospital admission? Ordinal variable [1-5]. 1 = No visible SAH. 2 = Maximum SAH thickness: ≤ 5 mm. 3 = Maximum SAH thickness: 5.1 mm to 10 mm. 4 = Maximum SAH thickness: 10.1 mm to 15 mm. 5 = Maximum SAH thickness: > 15 mm.
- n. Aneurysm therapy: What was the initial therapy to secure the aneurysm? Categorical variable [bypass, clipping, coiling, flow diverter, others, none]. Bypass = Aneurysm secured via trapping and bypass surgery. Clipping = Aneurysm secured via clipping. Coiling = Aneurysm secured via coiling. Flow diverter = Aneurysm secured with flow diverter. Others = Aneurysm secured via other treatment modality. None = Aneurysm not secured.

Hematoma volume: Continuous variable in [ccm] with one decimal figure, range 0.0 - 5000.0 ccm. Assessed on the initial CT scan in a second step. The CT scan will be uploaded by the local investigators in coded form (identifying information replaced by patient ID) to a HIN-secured platform provided by the sponsor, from where automated centralized quantification of hematoma volume is performed at the sponsor site. This is done blinded to the patients' study outcomes.

4.4.2 Monitoring period

4.4.2.1 CSF-sampling / CSF-Hb (Biomarker)

CSF sampling will be performed via EVD or LD, depending on the patient's access to the CSF space. The decision regarding the insertion of an EVD or LD is made independently of this study and according to the clinical standard of care. If an EVD or LD is present, 2ml of CSF will be sampled on a daily basis at approximately the same time in the morning. Immediately after sample collection, the CSF will be centrifuged at 1500 G for 15 minutes. The cell-free CSF supernatant will be stored at -80°C until analysis.

CSF-Hb measurements will be performed centralized in the Preclinical Research in Internal Medicine (PRIME) Laboratory, Wagistrasse 12, 8952 Schlieren (Switzerland). Absorption spectra in the visual range between 350 and 650 nm of all CSF samples will be measured. Quantification of oxyhemoglobin in CSF (CSF-Hb) will be performed using spectral deconvolution, as described previously^{12,14}. CSF-Hb will be handled as a continuous variable [mcmol/l].

4.4.2.2 Clinical assessment for secondary endpoints and safety endpoints

- a. The assessment will be performed on a daily basis between day 1 and day 14 post-SAH, always at approximately the same time of the day (afternoon) by a trained member of the clinical study team blinded to CSF sampling.
- b. Assessments for aVSP, DCI and DIND (components of the primary endpoint SAH-SBI, single secondary endpoints):
 - i. aVSP: The definition of aVSP comprises a narrowing of cerebral arteries based on a DSA,

- CTA or MRA. In the absence of an appropriate imaging procedure on the respective day, this will be noted as *no imaging performed*. Categorical variable [present, absent or no imaging performed].
- ii. DCI: Defined as new perfusion deficit or new infarction in native and/or contrast-enhanced CT/MRI. In the absence of an appropriate imaging procedure on the respective day, this will be noted as *no imaging performed*. Categorical variable [present, absent or no imaging performed].
 - iii. DIND: is defined as a new focal neurological deficit or a decrease in GCS of at least 2 points for at least 2 hours. In case the patient cannot be clinically assessed (e.g., sedation), this will be noted as *non-assessable*). Categorical variable [present, absent or non-assessable].
- c. Assessment for other secondary endpoints:
- i. Triple H therapy: Was a Triple-H-Therapy (or elements of it - i.e. hypertension, hypervolemia or hemodilution) induced within the last 24 hours? Categorical variable [no, yes].
 - ii. Spasmolysis: Was a rescue therapy with pharmacological spasmolysis or balloon angioplasty performed within the last 24 hours? Categorical variable [no, yes].
 - iii. Surgical decompression: Was a surgical decompression (e.g. decompressive hemicraniectomy) performed within the last 24 hours? Categorical variable [performed or not performed].
- d. Safety endpoints:
- i. CSF infection: Is there evidence for a CSF infection? Categorical variable [no, infection, colonization, contamination]. No = No symptoms or signs of CSF infection and no positive CSF culture. Infection = Clinical symptoms and signs of CSF infection and positive CSF culture. Colonization = 2 positive CSF cultures without clinical symptoms and signs. Contamination = 1 positive CSF culture without clinical symptoms and with consecutive culture being negative.
 - ii. Revision due to surgical site infection at the EVD skin entrance: Was a revision due to surgical site infection at the EVD/LD skin entrance performed within the last 24 hours? Categorical variable [no, yes]

4.4.3 Three months follow-up:

- a. The assessment will be performed at the 12 weeks (+/- 2 weeks) follow-up visit. This will be done on site if possible. If this is not possible, a consultation by telephone will be conducted.
 - b. Chronic hydrocephalus: The presence of chronic hydrocephalus is defined as the dependence on permanent CSF diversion which has not been needed before aneurysm rupture. If the patient had a permanent CSF diversion before aneurysm rupture, this will be noted as *shunt before aSAH*. Categorical variable [present, absent, shunt before aSAH].
- a. The following functional status scores will be assessed:
- i. Glasgow Outcome Scale Extended (GOSE): Ordinal variable [1-8]. 1 = Death. 2 = Vegetative state (unresponsive and speechless). 3 = Lower severe disability (requires frequent help of someone to be around at home most of the time every day). 4 = Upper severe disability (can be left alone > 8h during the day, but unable to travel and/or go shopping without assistance). 5 = Lower moderate disability (unable to work or only in sheltered workshop). 6 = Upper moderate disability (reduced work capacity; resumes < 50% of the pre-injury level of social and leisure activities). 7 = Lower good recovery (minor problems that affect daily life; resumes >50% of the pre-injury level of social and leisure activities). 8 = Upper good recovery (no current problems related to the brain injury that affect daily life).
 - ii. modified Rankin Scale (mRS): Ordinal variable [0-6]. 0 = No symptoms. 1 = No significant disability. Able to carry out all usual activities, despite some symptoms. 2 = Slight disability.

Able to look after own affairs without assistance, but unable to carry out all previous activities. 3 = Moderate disability. Requires some help, but able to walk unassisted. 4 = Moderately severe disability. Unable to attend to own bodily needs without assistance, and unable to walk unassisted. 5 = Severe disability. Requires constant nursing care and attention, bedridden, incontinent. 6 = Dead.

5 Sample Size

(ICH E3; 9.7.2. ICH E9; 3.5)

The primary objective of the study focuses on patients included with EVD while secondary objectives consider patients with both, EVD and LD as well as patients without any drainage system.

The sample size estimation is based on an effect size of 0.1, a power of 90% and accounts for between-site variability using a generalized linear mixed model. This calculation results in a minimum of 6 participating study sites and 30 patients per site with an EVD. Considering an anticipated drop-out rate of 15% and heterogeneous recruitment rates at the sites, we plan to include 8 sites and a maximal study population of 250 patients with EVD. Based on our clinical experience, we assume that only every second subject receives an EVD. Thus, we assume to include a maximum of 500 subjects. The recruitment will be stopped as soon as 250 patients with EVD are included.

6 General Analysis Considerations

6.1 Timing of Analyses

During the study, the central data monitor (CTU Berne, Switzerland) will check the eCRFs on a weekly basis and lock complete visits. No interim analysis will be performed. The final analysis will be conducted after completion of the study, i.e. when every patient has reached the 12 weeks follow-up, and data has been cleaned by the central data monitor.

6.2 Analysis Populations

(ICH E3; 9.7.1, 11.4.2.5. ICH E9; 5.2)

For analysis, the study population will be divided into the following three populations:

6.2.1 EVD cohort

Only those patients will be considered, where at least one CSF-sampling via an EVD (and CSF-Hb measurement) was performed between day 1 and day 14 post-SAH.

6.2.2 LD cohort

Only those patients will be considered, where at least one CSF-sampling via an LD (and CSF-Hb measurement) was performed between day 1 and day 14 post-SAH.

6.2.3 Full cohort

All included patients will be considered irrespective of their CSF-sampling status.

6.3 University Covariates and Subgroups

(ICH E3; 9.7.1, 11.4.2.1. ICH E9; 5.7)

6.3.1 Covariates:

- a. Study center: Categorical covariate with random intercepts.

- b. Subject ID: Categorical covariate with random intercepts.
- c. Day post-SAH: Categorical covariate.

6.3.2 Subgroups: Per-center analyses

(ICH E3;9.7.1, 11.4.2.4. ICH E9; 3.2)

Subgroup analyses will be performed per study center. Those centers will be included in subgroup analyses, where an EVD cohort of minimum 30 patients was reached.

6.4 Missing Data

(ICH E3; 9.7.1, 11.4.2.2. ICH E9;5.3. EMA Guideline on Missing Data in Confirmatory Clinical Trials)

Central and on-site data monitoring will be performed to reduce missing data. No imputation will be used.

Descriptive statistics on SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, DIND, triple H therapy, spasmolysis, surgical decompression, and 3 months-follow-up will include a missing data category (Template Table 2, Template Supplemental Table 5-6).

The extent and distribution of missing data for CSF-Hb, SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, DIND, chronic hydrocephalus, GOSE and mRS will be graphically represented in the following way:

- a. CSF-Hb:
 - i. Absolute stacked bar charts presenting the number of missing data points per day post-SAH (stratified by presence/absence/missing data on SAH-SBI/aVSP/DCI/DIND) in the EVD cohort (Template Figure 3B) and LD cohort (Template Supplemental Figure 3B).
 - ii. Absolute stacked bar charts presenting the number of missing data points per day post-SAH (stratified by presence/absence/missing data on chronic hydrocephalus, GOSE1-4/GOSE5-8/missing data and mRS0-3/mRS4-6/missing data) in the EVD cohort (Template Figure 4) and LD cohort (Template Supplemental Figure 4).
- b. SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, DIND:
 - i. Absolute stacked bar charts presenting the number of missing data points per day post-SAH in the EVD cohort (Template Figure 3A) and LD cohort (Template Supplemental Figure 3A).
 - ii. CSF-Hb values for the missing data category will be displayed as a separate category in the temporal boxplots of the EVD cohort (Template Figure 3B) and LD cohort (Template Supplemental Figure 3B).
 - iii. Next to the ROC curves, inverted violin plots will display the CSF-Hb values stratified by present, absent and missing clinical assessment in the EVD cohort (Template Figure 3D-F, Template Supplemental Figure 2D) and LD cohort (Template Supplemental Figure 3D-G).
- c. Chronic hydrocephalus, GOSE, mRS:
 - i. CSF-Hb values for the missing data category will be displayed as a separate category in the temporal boxplots of the EVD cohort (Template Figure 4) and LD cohort (Template Supplemental Figure 4).

6.5 Multiple Testing

(ICH E3; 9.7.1, 11.4.2.5. ICH E9; 2.2.5)

In the primary analysis, no adjustment of the significance level for multiple testing is needed.

No level of statistical significance will be defined for the secondary analyses. Instead, the results of secondary analyses will be interpreted based on the level of evidence ($p < 0.001$: very strong evidence; $p < 0.01$: strong evidence; $p < 0.05$ evidence; $p < 0.1$ weak evidence; $p > 0.1$: no evidence¹⁵) and confidence intervals will be provided, always in consideration of the multiple testing problem.

7 Summary of Study Data

Generally, all summary tables will be annotated with the relevant population size (EVD cohort, LD cohort, full cohort) and display any missing observations. The results will be structured in total (multicenter) cohort columns and columns for each study site.

7.1 Subject Disposition

A study flow diagram (Template Figure 1) will provide information on the following aspects:

- a. Enrollment: n screened, n excluded (incl. reasons for exclusion) and n included.
- b. Baseline assessment: n assessed.
- c. Monitoring: Clinical assessments for SAH-SBI (n assessments of n patients and n days on median), EVD CSF sampling (n samples of n patients and n days on median), LD CSF sampling (n samples of n patients and n days on median).
- d. 3-months follow-up: n lost to follow-up, n assessed at 3-months follow-up.
- e. Analysis: n EVD cohort, n LD cohort, n full cohort

7.2 Derived variables

The composite outcome SAH-SBI

The primary endpoint of this study is the occurrence of SAH-SBI. SAH-SBI is a categorical variable that will be derived as a composite from the categorical secondary endpoints aVSP, DCI, and DIND: If aVSP and/or DCI and/or DIND is/are present on the corresponding day, SAH-SBI is considered to be present. If neither information on aVSP (no imaging performed), nor DCI (no imaging performed) nor DIND (patient not clinically assessable) could be obtained, SAH-SBI is considered to be non-assessable. In any other instance, SAH-SBI is considered not to be present.

The grouped aneurysm location category *others*

For descriptive statistics (Template Table 1, Template Supplemental Table 2) and for secondary analyses (Template Figure 2), there will be a grouping of the following aneurysm locations into the category *others*: anterior choroidal artery, anterior inferior cerebellar artery, basilar artery aneurysm not involving the tip (e.g., pontine branches), non-paraophthalmic internal carotid artery (e.g., cavernous blisters), posterior cerebral artery, superior cerebellar artery, vertebral artery.

Functional outcome (GOSE, mRS) at 3 months follow-up

For the presentation of EVD and LD based CSF-Hb values stratified by GOSE and mRS (Template Figure 4, Template Supplemental Figure 4), the following dichotomization will be used:

- a. GOSE: dichotomization in 1-4 vs. 5-8.
- b. mRS: dichotomization in 0-3 vs. 4-6.

7.3 Protocol Deviations

The protocol deviations of the total (multicenter) cohort will be listed as reported by the study sites in Template Supplemental Table 1 as the following categories:

- a. Eligibility/Enrollment
- b. Informed consent
- c. Safety reporting
- d. Primary endpoint assessment
- e. Missed assessment
- f. Sampling

g. others

Each deviation will be briefly described with a free text.

7.4 Demographic and Baseline Variables

Continuous baseline variables (age, initial GCS, aneurysm size, hematoma volume) will be summarized using mean and standard deviation (Template Table 1, Template Supplemental Table 2).

Categorical baseline variables (sex, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, coronary artery disease, antithrombotics, smoking, pupil status, cranial nerve deficit, focal neurological deficit, headache, neck stiffness, WFNS grade, Hunt & Hess grade, aneurysm location, BNI grade, initial aneurysm therapy) will be summarized using frequency and percentages of observed levels (Template Table 1, Template Supplemental Table 2).

8 Endpoint Analyses

Descriptive statistics on CSF-Hb levels of Day 1 to Day 14 post-SAH will be provided as median, mean and SD for the EVD cohort and LD cohort of the total (multicenter) cohort (Template Supplemental Table 3) and each study site (Template Supplemental Table 4).

Descriptive statistics on SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, DIND, Triple H therapy, spasmolysis and surgical decompression are provided as absolute (n) and relative (%) incidence per patient and per day, whereas missing values are provided as separate category (Template Supplemental Table 5). The results are shown for the full cohort, the EVD cohort and the LD cohort.

Descriptive statistics on outcomes at 12-weeks follow-up (chronic hydrocephalus, GOSE, mRS) are provided as absolute (n) and relative (%) incidence per patient, whereas missing values are provided as separate category (Template Supplemental Table 6). The results are shown for the full cohort, the EVD cohort and the LD cohort.

8.1 Primary Endpoint Analysis

The null hypothesis is that there is no association between the concentration of EVD based CSF-Hb and the occurrence of SAH-SBI during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort. The confirmatory alternative hypothesis is that there is an association between the two.

The primary analysis evaluates the strength of association between SAH-SBI (dependent binary variable) and EVD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the EVD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts (Template Figure 3C). The likelihood ratio test p-value will be used to test the null hypothesis of no effect of the biomarker at a 5% significance level.

8.2 Secondary Endpoint Analyses

- a. Temporal profiles and dependence of EVD and lumbar drain (LD) based CSF-Hb
 - i. The temporal profile (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of EVD based CSF-Hb in the EVD cohort:
 - o Summary statistics as described in 8 (Template Supplemental Table 3, Template Supplemental Table 4).
 - o The temporal profile of EVD based CSF-Hb in the total (multicenter) EVD cohort will be visualized for each day post-SAH including boxplots for each day as summary-statistics (Template Figure 2A).

- The temporal profile of EVD based CSF-Hb in the EVD cohort stratified by study site will be visualized for each day post-SAH including boxplots for each day as summary-statistics (Template Supplemental Figure 1A).
- ii. The temporal profile (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of LD based CSF-Hb in the LD cohort.
 - Summary statistics as described in 8 (Template Supplemental Table 3, Template Supplemental Table 4).
 - The temporal profile of LD based CSF-Hb in the total (multicenter) LD cohort will be visualized for each day post-SAH including boxplots for each day as summary-statistics (Template Figure 2B).
 - The temporal profile of LD based CSF-Hb in the LD cohort stratified by study site will be visualized for each day post-SAH including boxplots for each day as summary-statistics (Template Supplemental Figure 1B).
- iii. Difference (per day and overall) between EVD and LD based CSF-Hb from day 1 to day 14 post-SAH.
 - For each day post-SAH, the difference in mean EVD based CSF-Hb and LD-based CSF-Hb is provided with its 95% confidence interval. Also, an overall mean of the difference in mean EVD based CSF-Hb and LD based CSF-Hb will be provided with its 95% confidence interval (Template Figure 2C, Template Supplemental Table 3).
- iv. The strength of association between EVD based CSF-Hb (continuous dependent variable) and aneurysm location (categorical independent variable), hematoma volume (continuous independent variable), presence of intraventricular hemorrhage (categorical independent variable), day post-SAH (continuous covariable, non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots) in the EVD cohort based on a GAM with repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts (Template Figure 2D).
- v. The strength of association between LD based CSF-Hb (continuous dependent variable) and aneurysm location (categorical independent variable), hematoma volume (continuous independent variable), presence of intraventricular hemorrhage (categorical independent variable), day post-SAH (continuous covariable, non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots) in the LD cohort based on a GAM with repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts (Template Figure 2E).
- b. EVD based CSF-Hb and SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND in the EVD cohort:
 - i. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND in the EVD cohort will be provided as absolute stacked bar charts stratified by the categories present, absent and no-imaging-performed/non-assessable (Template Figure 3A).
 - ii. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of EVD based CSF-Hb in the EVD cohort will be provided as temporal dot and box plots stratified by the presence, absence or no-imaging-performed/non-assessable of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, or DIND. Missing CSF-Hb measurements for each day in the EVD cohort will be shown below as an absolute stacked bar chart stratified by the presence, absence or no-imaging-performed/non-assessable of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, or DIND (Template Figure 3B).
 - iii. The strength of association between aVSP (dependent binary variable) and EVD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the EVD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time, and each study site accounted for with random intercepts (Template Supplemental Figure 2A).
 - iv. The strength of association between DCI (dependent binary variable) and EVD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the EVD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts (Template Supplemental Figure 2B).
 - v. The strength of association between DIND (dependent binary variable) and EVD based CSF-

- Hb (independent continuous variable) in the EVD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts (Template Supplemental Figure 2C).
- vi. The discrimination ability of EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort will be provided with ROC curves and corresponding AUC. The optimal Youden Index for each ROC curve will be calculated. For SAH-SBI, corresponding inverted violin plot visualizing the EVD based CSF-Hb values for each category (present, absent, missing) will be provided (Template Figure 3D).
 - vii. The discrimination ability of EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for the first occurrence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort will be provided with ROC curves and corresponding AUC. The optimal Youden Index for each ROC curve will be calculated. For SAH-SBI, a corresponding inverted violin plot visualizing the EVD based CSF-Hb values for each category (present, absent, missing) will be provided (Template Figure 3E).
 - viii. The discrimination ability of EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning of day X) for the first occurrence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of day X+1) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the EVD cohort will be provided with ROC curves and corresponding AUC. The optimal Youden Index for each ROC curve will be calculated. For SAH-SBI, a corresponding inverted violin plot visualizing the EVD based CSF-Hb values for each category (present, absent, missing) will be provided (Template Figure 3F).
 - ix. The discrimination ability of EVD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during day 4 and day 14 post-SAH in the EVD cohort will be provided with ROC curves and corresponding AUC. The optimal Youden Index for each ROC curve will be calculated. For SAH-SBI, a corresponding inverted violin plot visualizing the EVD based CSF-Hb values for each category (present, absent, missing) will be provided (Template Supplemental Figure 2E).
- c. LD based CSF-Hb and SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND in the LD cohort:
- i. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND in the LD cohort will be provided as absolute stacked bar charts stratified by the categories present, absent and no-imaging-performed/non-assessable (Template Supplemental Figure 3A).
 - ii. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of LD based CSF-Hb in the LD cohort will be provided as temporal dot and box plots stratified by the presence, absence or no-imaging-performed/non-assessable of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, or DIND. Missing CSF-Hb measurements for each day in the LD cohort will be shown below as an absolute stacked bar chart stratified by the presence, absence or no-imaging-performed/non-assessable of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, or DIND (Template Supplemental Figure 3B).
 - iii. The strength of association between SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND (dependent binary variables) and LD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the LD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts (Template Supplemental Figure 3C).
 - iv. The discrimination ability of LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the LD cohort will be provided with ROC curves and corresponding AUC. The optimal Youden Index for each ROC curve will be calculated. For SAH-SBI, a corresponding inverted violin plot visualizing the LD based CSF-Hb values for each category (present, absent, missing) will be provided (Template Supplemental Figure 3D).

- v. The discrimination ability of LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for the first occurrence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the LD cohort will be provided with ROC curves and corresponding AUC. The optimal Youden Index for each ROC curve will be calculated. For SAH-SBI, a corresponding inverted violin plot visualizing the LD based CSF-Hb values for each category (present, absent, missing) will be provided (Template Supplemental Figure 3E).
 - vi. The discrimination ability of LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning of day X) for the first occurrence of SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of day X+1) during the first 14 days post-SAH in the LD cohort will be provided with ROC curves and corresponding AUC. The optimal Youden Index for each ROC curve will be calculated. For SAH-SBI, a corresponding inverted violin plot visualizing the LD based CSF-Hb values for each category (present, absent, missing) will be provided (Template Supplemental Figure 3F).
 - vii. The discrimination ability of LD based CSF-Hb (measured in the morning) for SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI and DIND (assessed in the afternoon of the same day) during day 4 and day 14 post-SAH in the LD cohort will be provided with ROC curves and corresponding AUC. The optimal Youden Index for each ROC curve will be calculated. For SAH-SBI, corresponding inverted violin plot visualizing the LD based CSF-Hb values for each category (present, absent, missing) will be provided (Template Supplemental Figure 3G).
- d. EVD based CSF-Hb and 3-months follow-up status:
- i. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of EVD based CSF-Hb in the EVD cohort will be provided as temporal dot and box plots stratified by the presence, absence or non-assessability of chronic hydrocephalus at 3-months follow-up. Missing CSF-Hb measurements for each day in the EVD cohort will be shown below as an absolute stacked bar chart stratified by the presence, absence or non-assessability of chronic hydrocephalus (Template Figure 4A).
 - ii. The strength of association between chronic hydrocephalus at 3-months follow-up (dependent binary variables) and EVD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the EVD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts.
 - iii. The strength of association between EVD based CSF-Hb during the first 14 days post-SAH and functional outcome (GOSE, mRS) at 12 weeks follow-up in the EVD cohort.
 - iv. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of EVD based CSF-Hb in the EVD cohort will be provided as temporal dot and box plots stratified by the GOSE1-4, GOSE5-8 or non-assessability of GOSE scoring at 3-months follow-up. Missing CSF-Hb measurements for each day in the EVD cohort will be shown below as an absolute stacked bar chart stratified by GOSE1-4, GOSE5-8 or non-assessability of GOSE scoring (Template Figure 4B).
 - v. The strength of association between GOSE at 3-months follow-up (dependent categorical variable) and EVD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the EVD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts.
 - vi. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of EVD based CSF-Hb in the EVD cohort will be provided as temporal dot and box plots stratified by the mRS0-3, mRS4-8 or non-assessability of mRS scoring at 3-months follow-up. Missing CSF-Hb measurements for each day in the EVD cohort will be shown below as an absolute stacked bar chart stratified by mRS0-3, mRS4-8 or non-assessability of mRS scoring (Template Figure 4C).
 - vii. The strength of association between mRS at 3-months follow-up (dependent categorical variable) and EVD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the EVD cohort

based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts.

- e. LD based CSF-Hb and 3-months follow-up status:
- i. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of LD based CSF-Hb in the LD cohort will be provided as temporal dot and box plots stratified by the presence, absence or non-assessability of chronic hydrocephalus at 3-months follow-up. Missing CSF-Hb measurements for each day in the LD cohort will be shown below as an absolute stacked bar chart stratified by the presence, absence or non-assessability of chronic hydrocephalus (Template Supplemental Figure 4A).
 - ii. The strength of association between chronic hydrocephalus at 3-months follow-up (dependent binary variables) and LD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the LD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts.
 - iii. The strength of association between LD based CSF-Hb during the first 14 days post-SAH and functional outcome (GOSE, mRS) at 12 weeks follow-up in the LD cohort.
 - iv. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of LD based CSF-Hb in the LD cohort will be provided as temporal dot and box plots stratified by the GOSE1-4, GOSE5-8 or non-assessability of GOSE scoring at 3-months follow-up. Missing CSF-Hb measurements for each day in the LD cohort will be shown below as an absolute stacked bar chart stratified by GOSE1-4, GOSE5-8 or non-assessability of GOSE scoring (Template Supplemental Figure 4B).
 - v. The strength of association between GOSE at 3-months follow-up (dependent categorical variable) and LD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the LD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts.
 - vi. The temporal profiles (day 1 to day 14 post-SAH) of LD based CSF-Hb in the LD cohort will be provided as temporal dot and box plots stratified by the mRS0-3, mRS4-8 or non-assessability of mRS scoring at 3-months follow-up. Missing CSF-Hb measurements for each day in the LD cohort will be shown below as an absolute stacked bar chart stratified by mRS0-3, mRS4-8 or non-assessability of mRS scoring (Template Supplemental Figure 4C).
 - vii. The strength of association between mRS at 3-months follow-up (dependent categorical variable) and LD based CSF-Hb (independent continuous variable) in the LD cohort based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with day post-SAH as as continuous covariable (non-linear spline-fit with 4 knots), and repeated observations in the same patients over time and each study site accounted for with random intercepts.

9 Safety Analyses

9.1 CSF infection rate

Descriptive statistics on safety assessments (CSF infection, colonization, contamination, wound revision) will be provided as absolute (n) and relative (%) incidence per patient (Template Supplemental Table 7). The results are shown for the overall (multicenter) cohort and for each study site.

9.2 Serious Events

A serious event (SE) is defined as any clinical event where it cannot be excluded, that the event is attributable to the sampling of biological material or the collection of health-related personal data, and which:

- a. requires inpatient treatment not envisaged in the protocol or extends a current hospital stay,
- b. results in permanent or significant incapacity or disability, or
- c. is life-threatening or results in death.

A table of all reported serious events will be provided (Template Supplemental Table 8).

10 Reporting Conventions

P-values ≥ 0.001 will be reported to 3 decimal places; p-values less than 0.001 will be reported as “<0.001”. The mean, standard deviation, and any other statistics other than quantiles, will be reported to one decimal place greater than the original data. For the median, the same number of decimal places as the original data will be used. Estimated parameters will be reported to 3 significant figures.

11 Quality Assurance of Statistical Programming

Statistical analyses will be performed in R in an R studio environment on a Mac computer operating system¹⁶, applying dynamic reporting tools like RMarkdown or Sweave to guarantee highest standards of reproducibility. With this, the data and code will be directly linked to the study results.

The entire statistical code will be written by two authors (KA and RMB) for quality assurance (double programming). The study statistician (UH) will perform a review at the statistical programming code level, as well as on the report level. A second statistician will independently re-programme the primary analyses of the primary outcome. Guidelines for development and implementation will be followed.¹⁷

At the start of any code file there will be a set of comments that give

- the author
- the date and time of writing
- references to inputs and outputs
- reference to any parent code file that runs the child code file

Any outputs will have the

- date and time included
- the name of the code file that produced the analysis
- the author

12 Summary of Changes to the Protocol and/or SAP

This is the first version of the SAP (HeMoVal SAP V1.0, dated 22.10.2021).

13 References

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14 Template Figures

Template Figure 1 Study flowchart. *Daily CSF sampling in the morning (if EVD or LD present) and clinical assessment in the afternoon.

Template Figure 2 Temporal profiles and dependence of EVD and LD based CSF-Hb.

Template Figure 3 EVD based CSF-Hb and SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND.

Template Figure 4 EVD based CSF-Hb and 3-months follow-up.

15 Template Supplemental Figures

A EVD based CSF-Hb		B LD based CSF-Hb	
d1	d2	d1	d2
boxplot stratified by study site			
d3	d4	d3	d4
boxplot stratified by study site			
d5	d6	d5	d6
boxplot stratified by study site			
d7	d8	d7	d8
boxplot stratified by study site			
d9	d10	d9	d10
boxplot stratified by study site			
d11	d12	d11	d12
boxplot stratified by study site			
d13	d14	d13	d14
boxplot stratified by study site			

Template Supplemental Figure 1 EVD and LD based CSF-Hb on each day post-SAH stratified by study site.

Template Supplemental Figure 2 EVD based CSF-Hb and SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND (2).

Template Supplemental Figure 3 LD based CSF-Hb and SAH-SBI, aVSP, DCI, and DIND.

Template Supplemental Figure 4 LD based CSF-Hb and 3-months follow-up.

16 Template Tables

Template Table 1 Total cohort baseline characteristics.

Baseline characteristics of the total (multicenter) cohort. Detailed baseline features of the total and individual study center cohorts are provided in Supplemental Table 2. *Abbreviations:* ACA, anterior cerebral artery; ACOM, Anterior communicating artery; MCA, middle cerebral artery; PCOM, posterior communicating artery; PICA, posterior inferior cerebellar artery; WFNS, World Federation of Neurosurgical Societies.

		Full cohort	EVD cohort	LD cohort
n				
Age (mean, SD)				
Male sex (n, %)				
WFNS grade (n, %)	<i>I</i>			
	<i>II</i>			
	<i>III</i>			
	<i>IV</i>			
	<i>V</i>			
Aneurysm location (n, %)	<i>ACOM</i>			
	<i>Basilar tip</i>			
	<i>Distal ACA</i> ¹			
	<i>MCA</i>			
	<i>Paraophthalmic</i> ²			
	<i>PCOM</i>			
	<i>PICA</i>			
	<i>Others</i> ³			
Aneurysm size ⁴ (mean, SD)				
Intracerebral hemorrhage (n, %)				
Intraventricular hemorrhage ⁵ (n, %)				
Modified Fisher grade (n, %)	<i>1</i>			
	<i>2</i>			
	<i>3</i>			
	<i>4</i>			
Hematoma volume ⁶ (mean, SD)				
Aneurysm therapy (n, %)	<i>Bypass</i>			
	<i>Clipping</i>			
	<i>Coiling</i>			
	<i>Flow diverter</i>			
	<i>Others</i>			
	<i>None</i>			

¹distal to the anterior communicating artery (e.g., pericallosal artery, callosomarginal artery); ²ophthalmic or superior hypophyseal artery; ³anterior choroidal artery, anterior inferior cerebellar artery, basilar artery aneurysm not involving the tip (e.g., pontine branches), non-paraophthalmic internal carotid artery (e.g., cavernous blisters), posterior cerebral artery, superior cerebellar artery, vertebral artery; ⁴maximal diameter in mm; ⁵a hematoma bursting into the ventricular system was considered an intraventricular hemorrhage, while a pure retrograde redistribution of blood into the ventricular system was not; ⁶in cm³ based on automated segmentation and volumetry.

Template Table 2 Descriptive statistics on SAH-SBI-related outcomes.

Incidence of subarachnoid hemorrhage-related secondary brain injury (SAH-SBI, i.e., composite outcome composed of aVSP and/or DCI and/or DIND), angiographic vasospasms (aVSP), delayed cerebral ischemia (DCI), delayed ischemic neurological deficits (DIND), triple H therapy (induction of hypertension and/or hypervolemia and/or hemodilution), spasmolysis and surgical decompression (hemicraniectomy or suboccipital craniectomy) in the full cohort, external ventricular drain (EVD) and lumbar drain (LD) cohorts. The incidence is given per patient and per assessment day (p, present; a, absent; m, missing).

Outcome / Measure	Incidence											
	Full cohort			EVD cohort			LD cohort					
	Per patient	Per day			Per patient	Per day			Per patient	Per day		
		a	p	m		a	p	m		a	p	m
SAH-SBI												
aVSP												
DCI												
DIND												
Triple H therapy												
Spasmolysis												
Surgical decompression												

17 Template Supplemental Tables

Template Supplemental Table 1 Protocol deviations.

The protocol deviations of the total (multicenter) cohort are listed as reported by the study sites.

Study site	Category*	Description

*Categories: eligibility/enrollment, informed consent, safety reporting, primary endpoint assessment, missed assessment, sampling, other.

Template Supplemental Tables 2 Detailed baseline characteristics.

Detailed baseline characteristics of the total (multinational) cohort and the cohorts recruited at the individual study sites categorized in full cohort (F), EVD cohort (EVD) and LD cohort (LD). *Abbreviations:* ACA, anterior cerebral artery; ACOM, Anterior communicating artery; BNI, Barrow Neurological Institute; CAD, coronary artery disease; FND, focal neurological deficit; GCS, Glasgow Coma Scale; MCA, middle cerebral artery; PCOM, posterior communicating artery; PICA, posterior inferior cerebellar artery; WFNS, World Federation of Neurosurgical Societies.

		Overall (F/EVD/LD)	Site 1 (F/EVD/LD)	Site 2 (F/EVD/LD)	Site 3 (F/EVD/LD)	Site 4 (F/EVD/LD)	Site 5 (F/EVD/LD)	Site 6 (F/EVD/LD)	Site 7 (F/EVD/LD)	Site 8 (F/EVD/LD)
n										
Age (mean, SD)										
Male sex (n, %)										
MEDICAL HISTORY										
Diabetes mellitus (n, %)										
Hypertension (n, %)										
CAD (n, %)										
Antithrombotics (n, %)	<i>None</i>									
	<i>Antiplatelets</i>									
	<i>Anticoagulants</i>									
	<i>Combined therapy</i>									
Smoking (n, %)	<i>Never smoked</i>									
	<i>Quit smoking</i>									
	<i>Current smoker</i>									
CLINICAL PRESENTATION										
Initial GCS (mean, SD)										
Pupil status (n, %)	<i>Normal</i>									
	<i>Anisocoria</i>									
	<i>Bilateral mydriasis</i>									
Cranial nerve deficit (n, %)										
FND (n, %)	<i>None</i>									
	<i>Motor</i>									
	<i>Sensory</i>									

Headache (n, %)	<i>Combined</i>								
	<i>None</i>								
	<i>Mild</i>								
	<i>Moderate</i>								
Neck stiffness (n, %)	<i>Severe</i>								
	<i>None</i>								
	<i>Slight</i>								
WFNS grade (n, %)	<i>Pronounced</i>								
	<i>I</i>								
	<i>II</i>								
	<i>III</i>								
	<i>IV</i>								
Hunt & Hess grade (n, %)	<i>V</i>								
	<i>I</i>								
	<i>II</i>								
	<i>III</i>								
	<i>IV</i>								
RADIOLOGICAL FEATURES									
Aneurysm location (n, %)	<i>ACOM</i>								
	<i>Basilar tip</i>								
	<i>Distal ACA¹</i>								
	<i>MCA</i>								
	<i>Paraophthalmic²</i>								
	<i>PCOM</i>								
	<i>PICA</i>								
	<i>Others³</i>								
Aneurysm size⁴ (mean, SD)									
Intracerebral hemorrhage (n, %)									
Intraventricular hemorrhage⁵ (n, %)									

Modified Fisher grade (n, %)	1								
	2								
	3								
	4								
BNI grade (n, %)	1								
	2								
	3								
	4								
	5								
Hematoma volume ⁶ (mean, SD)									
Initial aneurysm therapy (n, %)	<i>Bypass</i>								
	<i>Clipping</i>								
	<i>Coiling</i>								
	<i>Flow diverter</i>								
	<i>Others</i>								
	<i>None</i>								

¹distal to the anterior communicating artery (e.g., pericallosal artery, callosomarginal artery); ²ophthalmic or superior hypophyseal artery; ³anterior choroidal artery, anterior inferior cerebellar artery, basilar artery aneurysm not involving the tip (e.g., pontine branches), non-paraophthalmic internal carotid artery (e.g., cavernous blisters), posterior cerebral artery, superior cerebellar artery, vertebral artery; ⁴maximal diameter in mm; ⁵a hematoma bursting into the ventricular system was considered an intraventricular hemorrhage, while a pure retrograde redistribution of blood into the ventricular system was not; ⁶in cm³ based on automated segmentation and volumetry.

Template Supplemental Table 3 Daily CSF-Hb levels within 14 days of aneurysm rupture.

The median, mean and the SD of CSF-Hb measurements (in μM) within the total (multicenter) EVD and LD cohorts stratified by day post-SAH. The difference in mean EVD based and LD based CSF-Hb is given with the corresponding 95% confidence interval and p-value (Mann-Whitney U test).

Day post-SAH	CSF-Hb: median, mean (SD) [μM]		
	EVD cohort	LD cohort	Difference in mean with 95% CI (p value)
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			
9			
10			
11			
12			
13			
14			
Summary	-	-	

Template Supplemental Table 4 CSF-Hb levels within 14 days of aneurysm rupture stratified by study site.

The median, mean and the SD of CSF-Hb measurements (in μM) of the EVD and LD cohorts stratified by day post-SAH and study site.

Day post-SAH	CSF-Hb (μM) per study site							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
EVD cohort								
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								
12								
13								
14								
LD cohort								
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								
12								
13								
14								

Template Supplemental Table 5 Descriptive statistics on SAH-SBI-related outcomes stratified by study site.

Incidence of subarachnoid hemorrhage-related secondary brain injury (SAH-SBI, i.e., composite outcome composed of aVSP and/or DCI and/or DIND), angiographic vasospasms (aVSP), delayed cerebral ischemia (DCI), delayed ischemic neurological deficits (DIND), triple H therapy (induction of hypertension and/or hypervolemia and/or hemodilution), spasmolysis and surgical decompression (hemicraniectomy or suboccipital craniectomy) in the full cohort, external ventricular drain (EVD) and lumbar drain (LD) cohorts. The absolute (n) and relative (%) incidence is given per patient and per assessment day (p, present; a, absent; m, missing).

Outcome / Measure	Incidence											
	Full cohort			EVD cohort			LD cohort					
	Per patient	Per day		Per patient	Per day		Per patient	Per day				
		a	p	m		a	p	m		a	p	m
Site 1, n												
SAH-SBI (n,%)												
aVSP (n,%)												
DCI (n,%)												
DIND (n,%)												
Triple H therapy (n,%)												
Spasmolysis (n,%)												
Surgical decompression (n,%)												
Site 2, n												
SAH-SBI (n,%)												
aVSP (n,%)												
DCI (n,%)												
DIND (n,%)												
Triple H therapy (n,%)												
Spasmolysis (n,%)												
Surgical decompression (n,%)												
Site 3, n												
SAH-SBI (n,%)												
aVSP (n,%)												
DCI (n,%)												
DIND (n,%)												
Triple H therapy (n,%)												
Spasmolysis (n,%)												
Surgical decompression (n,%)												
Site 4, n												

SAH-SBI (n,%)											
aVSP (n,%)											
DCI (n,%)											
DIND (n,%)											
Triple H therapy (n,%)											
Spasmolysis (n,%)											
Surgical decompression (n,%)											
Site 5, n											
SAH-SBI (n,%)											
aVSP (n,%)											
DCI (n,%)											
DIND (n,%)											
Triple H therapy (n,%)											
Spasmolysis (n,%)											
Surgical decompression (n,%)											
Site 6, n											
SAH-SBI (n,%)											
aVSP (n,%)											
DCI (n,%)											
DIND (n,%)											
Triple H therapy (n,%)											
Spasmolysis (n,%)											
Surgical decompression (n,%)											
Site 7, n											
SAH-SBI (n,%)											
aVSP (n,%)											
DCI (n,%)											
DIND (n,%)											
Triple H therapy (n,%)											
Spasmolysis (n,%)											
Surgical decompression (n,%)											
Site 8, n											
SAH-SBI (n,%)											
aVSP (n,%)											
DCI (n,%)											
DIND (n,%)											
Triple H therapy (n,%)											

Template Supplemental Table 6 Descriptive statistics on outcomes at three-months follow-up visits.

Incidence (n, %) of chronic hydrocephalus (defined as dependency on a ventriculoperitoneal shunt) and functional status (GOSE, Glasgow Outcome Scale-Extended; mRS, modified Rankin Scale) at three-months follow-up visits.

	Incidence (n, %)								
	Overall	Per study center							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Full cohort, n									
Chronic hydrocephalus									
(n,%)									
GOSE									
1 (n,%)									
2 (n,%)									
3 (n,%)									
4 (n,%)									
5 (n,%)									
6 (n,%)									
7 (n,%)									
8 (n,%)									
Lost to follow-up (n,%)									
mRS									
0 (n,%)									
1 (n,%)									
2 (n,%)									
3 (n,%)									
4 (n,%)									
5 (n,%)									
6 (n,%)									
Lost to follow-up (n,%)									
EVD cohort, n									
Chronic hydrocephalus									
(n,%)									
GOSE									
1 (n,%)									
2 (n,%)									
3 (n,%)									
4 (n,%)									
5 (n,%)									
6 (n,%)									
7 (n,%)									
8 (n,%)									
Lost to follow-up (n,%)									
mRS									
0 (n,%)									
1 (n,%)									
2 (n,%)									

3 (n,%)								
4 (n,%)								
5 (n,%)								
6 (n,%)								
Lost to follow-up (n,%)								
LD cohort, n								
Chronic hydrocephalus (n,%)								
GOSE								
1 (n,%)								
2 (n,%)								
3 (n,%)								
4 (n,%)								
5 (n,%)								
6 (n,%)								
7 (n,%)								
8 (n,%)								
Lost to follow-up (n,%)								
mRS								
0 (n,%)								
1 (n,%)								
2 (n,%)								
3 (n,%)								
4 (n,%)								
5 (n,%)								
6 (n,%)								
Lost to follow-up (n,%)								

Template Supplemental Table 7 Descriptive statistics on safety assessments.

Incidence (n, %) of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) infection (clinical symptoms and signs of CSF infection and positive CSF culture), colonization (two positive CSF cultures without clinical symptoms or signs), contamination (1 positive CSF culture with consecutive culture being negative) or wound revision due to surgical site infection at the EVD/LD skin entrance.

Safety endpoints	Incidence (per patient)								
	Overall	Per study site							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Full cohort, n									
CSF infection (n,%)									
Colonization (n,%)									
Contamination (n,%)									
Wound revision (n,%)									
EVD cohort, n									
CSF infection (n,%)									
Colonization (n,%)									
Contamination (n,%)									
Wound revision (n,%)									
LD cohort, n									
CSF infection (n,%)									
Colonization (n,%)									
Contamination (n,%)									
Wound revision (n,%)									

Template Supplemental Table 8 Reported serious events.

The protocol deviations of the total (multicenter) cohort are listed as reported by the study sites.

Study site	Serious Event Term	Seriousness criteria*	Description of the event	Intensity**	Causality with study***	Action taken****

*Categories: Event is life-threatening or results in death, Event results in permanent or significant incapacity or disability, Event requires inpatient treatment not envisaged in the protocol or extends a current hospital stay.

**Categories: Mild, Moderate, Severe, Life-threatening, Fatal.

***Categories: Data collection, Sampling of biological material.

****Categories: None, Study sampling modified, Study sampling discontinued, other